

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BHATTA****FIRST NAME: SHIV****PROGRAM CODE: DGG****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 1%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Office on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What differences can be seen in US and UK English?

- Punctuation.
- Initialization.
- Gramer.
- Spelling and Pronunciation.¹**

2. Why is it important to use sources for our research work?

- To become fair enough to use other's findings.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 25.

² *Ibid.*, 33-34.

- It is a common practice.
 - To prove our hypothesis.
 - To ease our work.
3. What are the essential things to understand before initiating research work?
- Reference materials.
 - University.
 - Professor.
 - Research topic and research question.**³
4. When are you supposed to cite a source?
- Because it ensures the data validity.
 - When using someone's findings or data.**⁴
 - Because it clarifies the research question.
 - Because it helps to identify the research hypothesis.
5. What is the best way to present our data?
- Cite someone's data.
 - Use quotations.
 - Table, bar chart, or line graph.**⁵

³ Ibid., 34-35.

⁴ Ibid., 34.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago, 2018), 181.

- Use of stories.
6. What can be a methodology for social surveys?
- Use of diverse theories.
- Principles and practices.
- Combination of both above.
- Qualitative, quantitative, or a combination of both.**⁶
7. What is a research argument?
- Write feelings properly.
- Give reasoning, provide evidence, and justify your own claim.**⁷
- Using maximum reference materials.
- Advisor's comments.
8. Which of the following is non-discriminatory language more important?
- Referring to disability.**⁸
- Respecting others.
- Use of widely used language.
- Use of common words.

⁶ James P. Sampson, *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 7.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian et al., 181.

⁸ WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. Second Edition (World Health Organization 2017), 55.

9. Which of the following is not a European Union member?

- Poland.
- France.
- Maldives.**⁹
- Germany.

10. What factors can contribute to making research successful?

- University you are associated with.
- Very good planning and communication.**¹⁰
- Questions posed.
- Your academic background.

⁹ European Union. *English Style Guide* (European Union, 2021), 96.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 14.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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